

Solid Fluorocarbon Lubricants

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Reprinted from February 1972 NLGI SPOKESMAN

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*Presented at the NLGI 39th Annual Meeting
in Philadelphia, Pa., October, 1971*

Introduction

The employment of the relatively expensive fluorocarbon lubricants is a result of their unique properties. The low speed coefficient of friction for PTFE and FEP (.04 - .06 is lower than graphite (.09) and molybdenum disulfide (.12). Further, the static coefficient of friction of PTFE is lower than the dynamic coefficient of friction, insuring non-stick-slip properties. The low surface energy of the fluorocarbon resins means that little shear energy is required to form a soft continuous film of lubricant. The compounds have low volatilities and unlike graphite, which requires a monolayer of water for maximum lubricity, can be used in high vacuum. The chemical resistance and lubricity of fluorocarbons is excellent over a temperature range from -400°F to 500°F. Antistick properties are another advantage—the critical surface tensions of fluorocarbon polymers are below the surface tensions of most liquids. A salient feature is the clean white color of the resins, allowing application in textile and pharmaceutical machinery.

At present there are two general classes of fluorocarbon lubricant powders, polytetrafluoroethylene and fluorinated ethylene-propylene copolymer. They are commonly referred to as TL (tetrafluoroethylene lubricant) powders without discriminating FEP bases. Powders are produced from these resins in a variety of ways including grinding (some at cryogenic temperatures), pyrolytic cracking, and molecular chain scission. While most of the technology is highly proprietary, our purpose is accomplished if it is understood that variation of process parameters within any single category can produce an entire range of powders. Differences exist among these powders that cannot be attributed merely to particle size. Only recently more advanced techniques have elucidated these differences. Prior to this understanding, a fluorocarbon's ability to lubricate was often considered to be inversely proportional to its particle size, and great pressure was brought upon producers to reduce particle size of the powders. While manufacturers worked to produce powders in the micron range, it was simultaneously observed that powders were working less efficiently in some of their old applications. This was particularly true in a few lace machinery applications where the old "standard" powders worked fine and newer sub-micron range powders demonstrated little utility. In the area of internally lubricated thermosets, new powders failed to disperse due to reduced particle size and variation in critical surface tension causing cracking and blistering of cured materials. The techniques by which powders were sized came into question. Material rated 7 microns average by one system could be rated 0.6 microns by another.

Characterization

SEM. A discussion of present characterization techniques is best initiated with the most powerful tool to

Figure 1—Most widely marketed powders have a larger particle size and dendritic configuration. (TL-115, 1000X)

recently enter the area of powder technology, the *scanning electron microscope*. A sample of lubricant powder is placed on a specimen mount. The entire mount is then vacuum metallized, most often with gold or platinum in order to produce a secondary surface a few Angstroms thick. The mount is then placed within the SEM and a primary electron beam is directed at it. Secondary electron emission is then scanned and transmitted on film or on a cathode tube. The cathode picture is invaluable in choosing sample site and sample magnification of interest.

Lubricant powders are most often characterized by particle size. The units generally employed are microns (10^{-4} cms) and refer to diameter of supposedly spherical particles. Figure 1 is a SEM of TL-115, a PTFE lubricant powder, the earliest one introduced and typical of the powders most widely marketed. It is used as a dry powder solid lubricant. The small dendritic particles are readily dispersed. It is used widely as a release agent when mixed with silicones in the rubber industry. Incorporation into thermosets and thermoplastics enhances PV, friction and wear properties. It is immediately obvious that definition by particle diameter (9 microns) is quite misleading. Particles are neither uniform nor round.

SEM's immediately reveal comparative particle sizes, particle configurations and suggest application suitability. TL-R (Figure 2) is a PTFE powder of extremely large particle size and irregular shape probably manufactured almost entirely by grinding. The powder would appear to have little utility in aerosols or coatings but is acceptable as an internal lubricant in plastics. TL-120 (Figure 3) is an FEP powder of substantial (50%) sub-micron size. Due to its extreme uniformity, low coeffi-

Figure 2—Less advanced powders are manufactured strictly by grinding. Particle configuration is highly irregular. (TL-R, 1000X)

cient of friction and high surface area, this material has gained acceptance in such diverse applications as a grease thickener and as a dry lubricant dusted on floors for bumper cars at amusement parks. While the material is excellent when dispersed in electrostatic coatings in order to impart low coefficient of friction, its extremely small spherical particle prevents its use in plastics and rubbers. Figure 4 depicts TL-102, the smallest particle PTFE powder presently manufactured. This material, manufactured by molecular chain scission is practically spherical, an excellent film former, and a preferred base for aerosols.

Although SEM's generate excellent first order approximations of particle size and distribution, little quantification of data is possible. In the first case, it is not easy to generate data for the amount of material photographed. In the second case, the sampling is necessarily small (< 50 nanograms) and not necessarily representative. Difficulty is encountered in estimating surface area of the particles and no indication of coefficient of friction and critical surface tension is given.

Particle Size

Traditionally, particle size is measured by finding the distribution of material on a series of sieves. The Tyler, U.S. Standard and Micromesh series are most widely known. For these, both mesh and wire gauge are specified. Mechanisms such as the gyratory riddle were developed in order to insure uniform agitation. More recently, devices such as the sonic sifter which agitate a series of screens at high frequency with intermittent pulsing have been introduced. These methods have little utility in the study of fluorocarbon lubricant powders.

Figure 3—An FEP powder generally has quite small particle size and rounded shape. (TL-120, 1000X)

The powders are at the small end of available sieve sizes and tend to resist sieving either by acquiring a static charge or by coating the sieve openings due to their ability to preform on metal surfaces. At present, sieving is seldom used. Appendix 1 compares sieve size, micron diameter, and true volume.

The Micromerograph has proven useful in characterizing particle size and distribution. The instrument operates by exploiting Stoke's law for particle sedimentation in air under the influence of gravity. For a spherical particle of given diameter and those particles of geometrical configuration that sediment equivalently

Figure 4—Molecular chain scission lubricants are nearly spherical. (TL-102, 1000X)

$$D^2\rho = \frac{18\mu S}{gt}$$

It may be noted that the density of air is considered negligible and is deleted

D = particle diameter

ρ = particle density

μ = gas viscosity

S = settling distance

T = settling time

g = acceleration of gravity

For particles of constant density, the equation simplifies to $D = \frac{K}{t}$ (K = constant) since the sedimentation

Figure 5—Hard, low critical surface tension powders tend to be granular. (TL-125, 1000X)

Figure 6—General purpose powders are intermediate between TL-102 and TL-115. (TL-126, 1000X)

Figure 7—Acicular configuration is the outstanding characteristic in bonded film lubricants. (TL-103, 1000X)

tion distance is constant. Operationally, the Micromerograph first deagglomerates the fluorocarbon powders by passing them through a slit and then allows them to sediment over a 7' column onto a weighing pan. The weight is recorded automatically as a function of time.

An example of the finished data is presented in Figure 8 for TL-102, for two runs of material from the same lot. Immediately evident is the high degree of instrument reproducibility. The even distribution of the powder indicates manufacturing uniformity. Powders produced strictly by grinding frequently demonstrate bimodal distributions, representing first and second passes through mills of different sizes.

Distribution range is in itself an interesting tool for judging appropriateness of application. A wider distribution range is generally found desirable for bonded film applications. TL-103F distribution is depicted in Figure 9. This wide range, elongated powder is being used successfully in these applications. Narrow ranges exhibited by TL-102 are useful in aerosol dispersions.

The disadvantages of the Micromerograph are greatest for small powders. For materials of density in the range of TL powders, the accuracy diminishes rapidly below 3 microns. The error contributes toward definition of larger particle average than actually exists. Aside from the expected instrumental error in weighing the smaller material, further error is due to accumulation of electrostatic charge on the particles and consequent adherence to the side of the sedimentation tube. The error is generally estimated to result in a 5% to 20% deficit in micron range material reported.

The Coulter Counter generates particle size distribution curves similar to those of the Micromerograph.

Figure 8—Low range distribution is illustrated by Micromerograph for lubricants employed in aerosols. (TL-102, 1000X)

The apparatus functions by measuring the increased resistance across an orifice as fluorocarbon particles dispersed in an electrolytic solution are drawn through by mild suction. The electrolyte has a constant conductivity. Non-conductive particles displace a volume of electrolyte and thus effect an increased resistance. The results are data based on the true volume of the particle which is then interpreted on the assumption of spherical volume to give a micron diameter. Since there is no simply calculable conductivity drop for a volume displacement, the Coulter Counter is calibrated with Mulberry pollen which has a particle size of 19-20 microns ($\sigma = \frac{1}{2}$ micron). Fluorocarbon lubricant powders are not wet by standard electrolytes and a surfactant must

Figure 9—Wide range distribution material is successfully employed in bonded films. (TL-103, 1000X)

Figure 10—The Coulter Counter distribution is similar to that of the Micromerograph for a typical lubricant powder. (TL-115, 1000X)

be added; alternately methanol-lithium chloride solution can be prepared as an electrolyte solution. Figure 10 is the Coulter Counter distribution for TL-115.

The principal operational difficulty with the Coulter Counter is the inability to maintain clean operating conditions. By the time the powder has been deagglomerated in the electrolyte in a separate ultrasonic unit and transferred to the beaker for a run, the mixture is certain to have accumulated dust particles. This results in a serious lack of definition for large particle sizes. Since one 100 micron particle of dust will balance out the volume of one million one micron particles of PTFE powder, assigning a proper particle distribution and average particle size is handicapped. Judicious operation, however, neglects a 100 micron particle when the remaining 99% of the particles are less than 30 microns.

The Fisher sub-sieve sizer is the most widely employed particle size apparatus. The values reported are average particle sizes only. The prevalence of Fisher data is not readily explained in terms of reliability or validity since the instrument does not measure particle size or a direct function of it. It may be explained in terms of cost and convenience. The sub-sieve sizer cost is \$500 while both the Micromerograph and Coulter Counter are \$8000. It takes 15 minutes to run the sub-sieve sizer while the Micromerograph takes three hours and the Coulter Counter takes one and one-half hours. The operation is quite simple. An amount of the fluorocarbon powder equal to its specific gravity in grams is compacted between two porous plugs in a 1/2" diameter column. A calibrated constant pressure of air is then exerted on one end of the sample and the pressure drop across the sample is indicated by a water manometer. The manometer height is positioned in front of a calibrated chart that allows direct readout of particle size. In practice, the Fisher sub-sieve sizer is measuring surface area as function of pressure drop.

Then particle diameter = $D = \frac{6 \times 10^4}{\rho(S)}$ for 1 cubic centimeter of material. (S = surface area, ρ = specific gravity).

The utility of the Fisher sub-sieve sizer does not rest upon its accuracy but upon its reproducibility. It is a convenient quality control tool and (when properly calibrated) is useful in generating specification values.

Surface Area is a useful parameter when used in conjunction with particle size distribution in estimating the surface roughness and covering area of a fluorocarbon powder. These properties are important when fluorocarbon lubricants are employed in dispersion applications, i.e., bonded films, greases and oil thickeners. The only successful method for determining surface area of fluorocarbons follows the BET (Brunauer, Emmet, Teller) extension for Langmuir monolayer adsorption. The BET derivation assumes that a given solid has a uniform surface, that a distinct number of adsorptive sites are available over the surface and that adsorbed monolayer molecules behave independently and provide sites for subsequent layers of adsorbed material which behaves as bulk liquid. The BET adsorptive description is

$$\frac{X}{V(I-X)} = \frac{I}{V_m C} + \frac{(C-1)X}{V_m C}$$

X = relative pressure = $\frac{P}{P_0}$; P_0 = pressure of

bulk condensation

V = volume adsorbed

V_m = volume of monolayer

C = temperature dependent constant (>1)

Operationally a sample of powder is placed within a sample tube and then thoroughly degassed at high vacuum. The sample tube is immersed in liquid nitrogen and helium (which is not adsorbed) is entered into the tube in order to make "dead space" calculations. The sample is re-evacuated, then opened to a known volume and pressure of nitrogen. The final pressure is recorded. The experiment is repeated at various pressures. Re-

turning to the BET equation $\frac{X}{V(I-X)}$ is plotted against X. The slope (S) and intercept I yield $V_m = \frac{I}{S+I}$ C = $I + \frac{S}{I}$. Given the cross-section-

al area of the nitrogen molecule as 15.8 Å², the surface area may be calculated. The Perkin-Elmer Sorptometer is an available instrument for performing this experiment.

For bonded films, larger particles with relatively high surface areas are most successfully employed. This includes primarily TL-126 and TL-103. The latter is more acicular in particle configuration than most lubricants. Low surface area materials like TL-115 are often added to thermosets and thermoplastic compounds since they have little effect on the viscosity of the resin and are better able to contribute to formation of a fluorocarbon film during wear-in of the finished part.

TL-120 because of its extremely high surface area has been employed as a pigment in paint for the F-111 fighter plane.

Coefficient of Friction is a parameter directly associated with the lubricity of a material. Although there are several acceptable tests for evaluating the coefficient of friction of fabricated materials, the only satisfactory system for evaluating boundary lubricants to achieve wide acceptance is the compression-fit test developed by Dow Corning (LFW-4). In this test, the lubricant is burnished onto a 0.7510" pin. The pin is then pressed into a similarly burnished 0.7500" I.D. bushing at a constant speed of 0.6"/min. The maximum force exerted can be used to calculate the coefficient of friction, since

$$f = \frac{F}{Ln}$$

f = coefficient of friction
 F = maximum force exerted
 in pushing pin through (lbs.)
 Ln = normal load (lbs.)

The normal load is calculated from the interference (δ) and expansion of the bushing as follows:

$$P_i = \frac{E\delta}{2D^2d} \quad (D^2 - d^2)$$

P_i = press-fit pressure
 (applied to pin by bushings)

E = modulus of elasticity
 (29.5×10^6 for hard
 steel standard)

D = O.D. of bushing 1.125"

d = I.D. of bushing .750"

$\delta = \frac{D}{d} \Delta D$ = interference

ΔD = bushing expansion

bushing length = 1.75"

This reduces to a simple expression for which only the maximum force applied and change in diameter are substituted

$$f = \frac{F}{6.5 \times 10^7 \Delta D}$$

Under typical conditions, the compression-fit test develops a low speed coefficient of friction for loads in

excess of 10,000 psi. Fluorocarbon lubricants are generally employed at stress levels below this, but data generated for the powders (Table 1) indicate the coefficient of friction remains low—between 0.04 and 0.14.

The Bowden-Leben test method for fabricated material generally assigns a value of 0.04 to PTFE and 0.06 to FEP. The fact that TL-120, an FEP powder, demonstrates a lower coefficient of friction than many PTFE powders probably reflects its ability to be burnished into the pin and bushing surfaces.

TL-102 exhibits the lowest coefficient of any fluorocarbon powder tested. This is probably a function of its process method (molecular chain scission) which leaves a soft, easily burnished particle, of small size and high critical surface tension. It is adapted to lubrication of delicate instruments associated with timing and weaponry. In high speed, long term applications it is sometimes deficient because the light spherical particles tend to blow off before they are burnished into the surface.

The chief difficulty with the compression-fit test is the necessity of burnishing a compound into a metal surface. Many applications employ the lubricant between two surfaces in sliding contact. While a lubricant is typically sandwiched in and burnished by the contacts, the compression-fit shears the lubricant perpendicular to its direction of action. The method also gives no indication of the particular properties of PTFE lubricants. The coefficient of friction for solid fluorocarbon lubricants decreases with increasing loads. The dynamic coefficient of friction is greater than the static coefficient of friction (0.04 and 0.02 for PTFE, respectively). The coefficient of friction for fluorocarbon powders has been shown to be independent of temperature up to their melting point.

Critical Surface Tension like coefficient of friction is a parameter directly associated with the lubricity of a material. Additionally, it furnishes information on the behavior of fluorocarbon powders in aerosol dispersions, oils, greases, and resin binders. Liquids with surface tensions below the critical surface tension γ_c of a solid

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will wet-out a surface and show a contact angle of 0 ($\text{COS } \theta_e = 1$). The critical surface tension is unique for any solid. The contact angle θ_e is given by Young's equation

$$\gamma_C - \gamma_{S1} = \gamma_1 \text{COS } \theta_e$$

γ_{S1} = interfacial surface tension
 γ_1 = surface tension of liquid

The contact angle is determined by compressing the fluorocarbon powder at 2,000 psi into a block and determining height (h) and radius (x) of a drop of n-dodecane

$$\theta_e = 2 \tan^{-1} \frac{h}{x}$$

The goniometer is employed to determine the contact angle.

Table 2 presents the surface tensions of common solvents and oil bases along with the critical surface tensions of various fluorocarbon powders. Other low critical surface tension polymers are included for reference.

Since oils have surface tensions greater than fluorocarbon lubricants, a complete wet-out is not effected. The powders with higher critical surface tensions are wetted to a greater extent than those of lower critical surface tension. The total thixotropic action of these materials may be predicted by using critical surface tension along with surface area data. TL-120, an FEP powder, exhibits the greatest thixotropic action demonstrating a γ_C of 21.9 dynes/cm and a surface area of 10.1 meters²/gram. The higher cost of this material has limited its use to silicone and fluorosilicone oils. Surprisingly TL-125, a PTFE powder with relatively low surface area, has been used successfully as a grease thickener.

In aerosols the disperant as well as the propellant must have a surface tension below that required to effect complete wet-out of the resin. It is advantageous to employ liquids of high density to deter settling of the lubricant powders. Freon 12 and Freon 113 are most frequently employed with a powder like TL-102. It

Table 1—Fluorocarbon Lubricant (TL) Properties

Designation	Units	TL-102	TL-103F	TL-115	TL-120	TL-125	TL-126
Polymer Base		PTFE	PTFE	PTFE	FEP	PTFE	PTFE
Specific Gravity		2.18 to 2.28	2.18 to 2.28	2.15 to 2.20	2.12 to 2.18	2.16 to 2.24	2.16 to 2.28
Particle Size Micromerograph	microns ± 2 microns						
Maximum		17	28	34	16	32	24
90% below		13	18	20	10	20	16
50% below		5	8	10	2	10	8
Coulter Counter	microns ± 2 microns						
Maximum		20	32	33	19	26	20
90% below		14	20	16	10	15	16
50% below		3	9	8	2	7	6
Scanning Electron Microscope	microns	3 to 8	8 to 30	6 to 25	1 to 2	8 to 25	6 to 25
Fisher Sub-sieve Sizer		1 to 2	1 to 4	1 to 4	<1	1 to 4	1 to 3
Surface Area	meters ² /gram ± .5 m ² /g	7.6	5.3	1.2	10.1	2.1	6.5
Coefficient of Friction		.06 to .08	.07 to .11	.08 to .14	.07 to .10	.08 to .12	.06 to .012
Critical Surface Tension	dynes/cm ± .2 dynes/cm	20.9	20.7	19.4	21.9	21.5	20.2
Bulk Density (Uncompacted)	grams/liter (± 25g/l)	425	525	475	400	425	400
Useful Temperature Range	°F	—400 to +500	—400 to +500	—400 to +500	—400 to +450	—400 to +500	—400 to +500
Oil Absorption ASTM D1483	lbs. oil/ 100 lbs. TL	40.9	43.9	34.7	47.3	44.4	38.4

should be noted that aerosols with large nozzle orifices may allow agglomeration of small particles. The small particle size and high γ_c of TL-102 has allowed its utilization as an anti-scuff agent for printing inks when incorporated at levels varying from 1-5%. The ability of fluorocarbon powders to behave as release agents is very often attributable to their generally low critical surface tension. Thus, rubber rollers compounded with

TL-126 and TL-115 PTFE powders are employed in the printing and food manufacturing industries. They have also been employed for green tire release agents and high temperature thermoplastic mold release agents.

The critical surface tension of fluorocarbon lubricants decreases with increasing temperature so that release agent activity is improved at higher temperatures.

Table 2—Surface Tension Comparison

Solid Polymer	Critical Surface Tension dynes/cm	Liquid Surface Tension dynes/cm	Liquid
		9.0	Dichlorodifluoromethane (Freon 12)
		12.5	Dichlorotetrafluoroethane (Freon 114)
		16.2	Methyl chloride
		16.0-16.7	Perfluoroalkylethers low MW (Krytox 143AZ-143AA)
		17.3	Carbon tetrachloride
		17.3	Trichlorotrifluoroethane (Freon 113)
		18.2	n-propyl chloride
		18.4	n-hexane
		17.7-18.5	Perfluoroalkylethers medium MW (Krytox)
Polytetrafluoroethylene	18.5	19.0	Trichlorofluoromethane (Freon 11)
		19.3-20	Perfluoroalkylethers high MW (Krytox, Fomblin)
TL-115 PTFE	19.4	19.7	n-butylamine
		19.9	Polydimethylsiloxane (pentamer)
TL-126 PTFE	20.2	20.4	n-heptane
TL-103 PTFE	20.7	20.7	t-butanol
TL-102 PTFE	20.9		
		21.2	Acetaldehyde
TL-125 PTFE	21.5	21.8	n-octane
TL-120 FEP	21.9	22.3	Ethanol
		22.6	Methanol
		24.0	n-decane
		24.2	Ethylene dichloride
Polytrifluoroethylene	25.0	25.4	n-dodecane
		26.5	Methylene chloride
		26.7	n-tetradecane
Polyvinylfluoride	28.0	28.8	Benzene
		30-32	400 MW mineral oil
Polyethylene	31.0		
Polychlorotrifluoroethylene	31.0		
		32.3	Carbon disulfide
Polystyrene	33.0		
Polyvinyl Alcohol	37.0		
Polyvinyl Chloride	39.0		
Nylon 11	39.0		
		72.5	Water

Oil Absorption

Oil absorption number provides a direct test for the relative absorption action of TL's. Critical surface tension and surface area generate useful but, in many instances, inconclusive data which oil absorption tests can resolve. This method (ASTM D-1483) involves titration of linseed oil onto a known amount of TL until free oil appears. The number reported as pounds of oil per 100 lbs. of TL. Both critical surface tension and surface area indicate that TL-120 and TL-115 would have the greatest and least thickening action, respectively. This is supported by oil absorption data in Table 1. One unusual result is the relatively high thickening action of TL-125. Surface area measurements suggest poor results but actual results show high sensitivity to critical surface tension.

These data suggest that the utility of various TL's in grease compositions would be TL-120 > TL-125 > TL-103f > TL-102 > TL-126 > TL-115. This order is affected by the volume of material tested. In this method of evaluation TL-102, for example, is present in larger volume than TL-103f, although weights are the same. Bulk densities are reported in Table 1. At low levels of addition, bulk density is of lesser importance since intensive dispersion would give results dependent on actual particle density. At higher levels where process parameters are more important, bulk density as well as particle configuration become more important. For these reasons, TL-102 should rise in our ranking and also, to a lesser degree, TL-126.

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Appendix 1—Particle Size Measure

Micron Diameter	Inch Diameter	Mesh Tyler	Mesh U.S. Stand.	Volume micromicroliters
75	.0029	*	*	220,000
74	.0029	200	200	212,000
66	.0026	*	*	150,000
63	.0025	*	*	131,000
62	.0024	*	230	124,000
61	.0024	250	*	119,000
60	.0023	*	*	113,000
53	.0021	270	270	78,000
50	.0020	*	*	65,000
44	.0017	*	325	44,500
43	.0017	325	*	41,500
40	.0016	*	*	33,500
37	.0014	*	400	26,500
30	.0012	*	*	14,100
25	.0010	*	*	8,200
20	.0008	*	625	4,180
15	.0006	*	*	1,760
10	.0004	*	1250	520
5	.0002	*	2500	65
2.5	.0001	*	5000	8
1.0	.00004	*	12500	5